

The Role of Education in Empowering Girl Child along the Coastal Areas of Tanzania: A Case of Salale Ward in Kibiti District Council

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6602392>

Published Date: 01-June-2022

Abstract: This paper examines the role of education in empowering girl child along the coastal areas of Tanzania. The study intends to ascertain the culture of coastal communities and cultural correlation of coastal communities to the role of education in empowering girl child. This study adopted a qualitative research approach to obtain data on the culture of coastal communities and its correlation to the role of education in empowering girl child. The researchers relied on observation, in-depth interview and focus group discussion for all the data collected. Data processing and analysis encompassed several stages. The N-Vivo version 11 software helped sort and organize raw data collected in the field work; this includes coding and identifying themes and subthemes. A ground theory approach to data analysis was employed to facilitate open coding and a constant comparison methodology. The grounded theory process entails a careful reading of data to gain in-depth familiarity with it, and subsequently identify key concepts and emerging issues. Findings of the study revealed that cultural practices in coastal areas include initiation ceremony to girls, involving girls in fishing and petty trading as a means of gaining income, and education is given priority to boys rather than girls. It was further revealed that some cultural practice in coastal communities resulted to the need of educating the society on the importances' of education among girls. This is because through education they will be independent, confident and capable of dealing with life challenges' in the contemporary society. This study among others, recommends that education should be given to a girl child in coastal communities in the same bases as boys given, some cultural practices should be stopped by educating parents, education should be taken as a priority to both boys and girls in coastal communities.

Keywords: Role of education, empowerment, girl child and Coastal areas.

1. INTRODUCTION

Girls' access to education has increasingly become a global concern (Bali & Mbavai, 2015). This is due to the understanding that education is the only tool for realising individual, national and global development. Education is considered the most important tool for empowering women and girls in the society. Education is not only limited to developing personality of an individual, but also plays an important role in economic, social and cultural development (UNESCO, 2015). Education is the mile stone of girl's empowerment as it enables them to respond to the challenges, to confront their traditional role and change their life. It has been further stated in the UN fifth sustainable development goals that gender equity is crucial. In that, women and girls worldwide have significantly less access to education than their male counter parts. 66% of the world's 774 million illiterate population are women (UNESCO, 2014). This overwhelming statistics calls for global necessity of education for women and girls. Ban Ki-Moon, former United Nations Secretary General, once acknowledged that wise investments in education can transform individual's life, national economies and our world (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization-UNESCO, 2014).

In 2000, 164 governments agreed on the Dakar Framework for Action, EFA at the World Education Forum in Dakar, Senegal (UNESCO, 2015). Reaching the marginalised groups such as children with special needs, from disadvantaged ethnic minorities, remote and isolated communities was among the strategies to achieve the Dakar Framework. With goal number 5, gender parity and equality, the framework focused on ensuring girls' full and equal access to basic education by 2015 (UNESCO, 2015). The post 2015 Sustainable Development Goals by the United Nations, goal number 4 and 5 (Osborn, Cutter & Ullah, 2015) emphasize on girls' education to attain gender equality and equity for sustained development by 2030.

This study was informed by human right theory in analyzing girls' education. In that, education was viewed as a basic and fundamental right for every person. This is due to the idea that education is the source of knowledge and contributes to the development of human personality (Beiter, 2006). The United Nations recognizes education as a human right in Article 26 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948 (Donnelly, 2013). The right to education has been further documented by UNESCO and international laws (UNICEF, 2007).

In addition, the right to education is provided in Article 13 of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights of 1966 (Beiter, 2006). The goal of this human right-based approach to education is to assure every child gets quality education that respects and promotes her or his right to dignity and optimum development (UNICEF, 2007). It has been further stipulated in UNICEF framework (2007) that there are three dimensions of human right-based approach to education: right to access education, right to quality education and right to respect within education system. These three dimensions should be considered when developing strategies to improve girls' education. In this paper, coastal culture was considered as the hindering factor for the girls' access to education which undermines girls' rights.

In Tanzania, only 69% of girls' transit from primary to lower secondary education compared to 73% of boys, according to UNESCO Institute for Statistics (2017). This is associated with less support from the family, lack of confidence, gender based violence (GBV) and adolescent pregnancy. Kibiti district council had only 78 public pre-primary schools, no private pre primary schools exist. The number of public owned pre-primary schools remained constant from 2015 to 2017. The largest number of public pre-primary schools in the council was at Bungu ward (6) and Mwambao ward (6), while Maporoni ward had only 2 public pre primary schools. Additionally, Salale is among the wards found in Kibiti District Council. The ward is highly involved in fishing activities as it is located along the Indian Ocean. The ward has 6 public primary schools and 2 public secondary schools. In Kibiti district, truancy is the leading source of drop out followed by pregnancy and other reasons. (Kibiti District Profile, 2018).

The Problem

Empowerment is viewed as means of creating a social environment in which one can make decisions and choices either individually or collectively for social transformation. The empowerment strengthens the innate ability by the way of acquiring knowledge, power and experience (Suguna, 2011). It is the process by which one gets control over one's destiny, and the circumstances of one's lives. As a process, empowerment is closely related to education, since education modified one's behaviour in every aspect such as mentality, outlook and attitude. On the contrary, girls are presented as not being able to access education on the equal chance as boys specifically in coastal communities (Evans *et al.*, 2009). Scholars have associated this gender disparity to cultural norms (UNESCO, 2003). Others have pointed out fingers to the economy (UNESCO, 2000), and others to political inadequacy of education services. Literatures have revealed that many girls in different societies are still lagging behind in acquiring education. This affects not only their standard of living, but also their accessibility to basic needs and services.

Bhalalusesa (2001) and Misra (2005) for instance found socialization into gender specific roles as contributing factor in gender disparity in society. Furthermore, cultural values like early marriages for girls (Almunajjed, 2009), negative attitude towards smart girls, different treatment of girls than boys (Douglas, 2007), and parents having different aspiration for boys than girls affect girls' education (Evans *et al.*, 2009). These socio-cultural factors have contributed to lagging behind for girls in education. While these facts above point to broader views of factors impacting on gender disparity in education, there is little focus on how coastal cultural correlates to the role of education in empowering girl child in coastal areas. Tanzania has a coastline of over 800km of the Indian Ocean, in that there are five administrative regions situated along the mainland coast. That includes Tanga, Pwani, Dar es Salaam, Lindi and Mtwara. These regions are further distributed into districts. The five coastal regions cover 15 percent of the country's total land area, and 25 percent of the country's population (Census report, 2012). Economic activity is high in some coastal regions. The five coastal

regions contributed about one-third of the national Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Dar es Salaam is leading with 20 percent of the GDP. However, Lindi and Pwani regions are ranked low in terms of contribution in the Gross Domestic Product (URT, 2012). In this study, coastal are categorized as a group of people who live in a coastal area and the source of their economic life depends on the utilization of marine and coastal resources (Mangora & Shalli, 2006). Social and cultural aspects of a society form its very nature. As culture, is the essence of a society so as the coastal cultural settings. With that background, this study aimed to understand the role of education in empowering girl child along the coastal areas. Specifically, the study intends to identify the culture of coastal communities, as well as to establish its correlation to the role of education in empowering girl child in Kibiti district.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The Study Area

This study was conducted at Salale ward within Kibiti district council. The area was purposively selected because the area is located along the Indian Ocean and its locals are mainly involved in artisan fishing, cultivation of rice for substances, petty trading and charcoal making as their main economic activities (Kibiti District Council Profile, 2018). Also, the truancy level is high to students of both primary and secondary schools (Kibiti District Council Profile, 2018). This study targeted education officers, primary and secondary school teachers, and village leaders such as village executive officers, village chairperson, ward executive officer, ward education officer and parents as key informants. Additionally, students from both primary and secondary schools were involved in this study. The area has six primary schools and two secondary schools, the two secondary schools are found in Nyamisati village.

Figure 1: Map showing the study area

Data Collection

In this study, in-depth interviews to the key informants, focus group discussion and observation were deployed to collect requisite data. Both primary and secondary data were collected. The main source of data and information for this study was primary data collected at three different levels. First, in-depth interview were conducted to the key informants that include ward executive officer, ward education officer, head teachers, headmistress, village chair persons and village executive officers. These key informants were purposefully selected as they were familiar with the topic under study, but again they are familiar with the study area. Second, focus group discussion was conducted to selected students of both primary and secondary schools as well as male and female parents found in the study area. Third, observation was also utilized throughout the entire process of data collection, this method focused on observing major livelihood activities in

the area, various cultural practises, and daily routines of community members. Data collection instruments included a checklist for the in-depth interview to the key informants and a check list for the focus group discussion as well. Documentary review was also used in this study such various reports from UNESCO, UNICEF and UNDP

Information collected in the in-depth interviews included common cultural practises found in coastal communities, main economic activities found in the area, how cultural practise correlates with education provision in the area, specifically provision of education among girls, importance of education and suggestions to the government on the education provision to girls. While the information collected in the focus group discussion included common cultural practise found in coastal communities, challenges facing girls in coastal communities in the course of getting their education, factors associated with gender disparity in education provision in coastal communities, implications of main economic activities found in the study area and the provision of education to children and correlation of cultural practises and education provision to girls in coastal communities.

3. DATA ANALYSIS

The process of data analysis began in the initial stage of data collection process, whereby data interpretation were conducted by narrowing collected data into smaller and important groups of key data (Berg, 2001). Data processing encompassed several stages. The N-Vivo version 11 software helped to sort and organize raw data collected in the field work; this included coding and identifying themes and sub – themes. A ground theory approach to data analysis was employed to facilitate open coding and a constant comparison methodology. The grounded theory process entails a careful reading of data to gain in-depth familiarity with it and subsequently identify key concepts and emerging issues (Hammersley & Atkinson, 1997). This was followed by the utilization of the ‘constant comparative method’ (Glaser and Strauss 1967 in Corbin and Strauss 1990), which requires finding explicit meaning and exploring the relation within and among each category. In that, data were compared and contrasted to explore both similarities and differences on the correlation of coastal communities to the role of education in empowering girl child.

The Approach

This study was guided by a qualitative approach as it intends to understand concepts, opinion and experiences of local in the coastal communities. In that, in-depth interviews, observation and focus group discussion were used in data collection process so as to obtain an in - depth understanding of the topic under study. In this approach ground theory has been used so to establish difference and similarities to the collected data. This approach enables to researcher to asses everyday community life from the participants’ perspective (Berg, 2001). This study focused on identification of culture in coastal communities and establishment of its correlation of coastal communities to the role of education in empowering girl child. This study adopted a qualitative research approach to obtain data on culture of coastal communities and culture correlation to the role of education in empowering girl child.

Table 1: Number of interviews, distribution along the study area and demographics’ of respondents.

Method	Category of Participants	Study Area					
		Nyamisati Village	Mfisini Village	Kiomboni Village	Salale Village	Saninga Village	Mchinga Village
In-depth interviews	Key Informants						
	Ward Executive Officer 1(Male)	1(Male)					
	Ward Education Officer 1(Male)	1 (Male)					
	Head teachers 6(Males)	1 (Male)	1(Male)	1(Male)	1(Male)	1(Male)	1(Male)
	Headmistress 2(Females)	2 (Females)					
	Village Executive Officers 6 (Males)	1(Male)	1(Male)	1(Male)	1(Male)	1(Male)	1(Male)
	Village Chairperson 6 (Males)	1(Male)	1(Male)	1(Male)	1(Male)	1(Male)	1(Male)

Source: Field Data, Jan 2022

Table 2: Number of interviews, distribution along the study area and demographics' of respondents.

Method	Study Area					
	Mfisini Village	Kiomboni Village	Salale Village	Saninga Village	Mchinga Village	Nyamisati Village
Focus Group Discussion (FGD) to primary and secondary schools						
Primary	10 Males 10 Females	10 Males 10 Females	10 Males 10 Females	10 Males 10 Females	10 Males 10 Females	10 Males 10 Females
Secondary	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	10 Males 10 Females from Nyamisati Secondary
	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	20 Females from Wama Nakayama Girls High School
Parents FGD	10 Male Parents 10 Female Parents					

Source: Field Data, Jan 2022

A total of 10 focus group discussions were conducted in six villages over a period of one month focused to students of both primary and secondary schools and the two groups of parents. Focus group discussion was conducted to selected students of primary and secondary schools as well as male and female parents found in the study area. While in-depth interview were conducted to the key informants was conducted to ward executive officer, ward education officer, head teachers, headmistress, village chair persons and village executive officers. These key informants were purposefully selected as they were familiar with the topic under study, but again they are familiar with the study area. In that, respondents participated in focus group discussion were 10 male students and 10 females' students in primary school while other 10 male students and 10 female students participated in the focus group discussion in Nyamisati secondary school and 20 female students participated in the focus group discussion from Wama Nakayama Girls High school. Participants participated in the focus group discussion demonstrated a more in-depth understanding of the topic under study. was also utilized throughout the entire process of data collection. Observation was also conducted in the entire process of data collection.

Ethical Consideration

Prior data collection, all procedures related to gaining permission to carry out the study, which involved human subjects were followed. This included receiving final research clearances from all relevant authorities. In the field, researcher ensured informed consent by providing clear explanation on the objectives of this study to the informants and ensuring that each participant understood that their participation was voluntary and that information they shared would remain confidential and only be used for this study. In order to ensure confidentiality, pseudonyms were used in the study.

4. FINDINGS

In reading and making comparisons, several concepts and themes were identified. Examples of concepts identified include '*kuchezwa ngoma*' - initiation ceremony to girls, *jamii iliyojitenga* - 'homogenous society' and '*kambi za uvuvi na kilimo*' - fishing and farming camps. In coding interviews, several themes started to emerge related to the culture of coastal communities and its correlation to the role of education in empowering girl child.

A total of five themes emerged:

- Initiation ceremony is a rite of passage to all girls;
- Education is provided more to boys rather than girls as they are assumed to be responsible in taking care of old parents;

- Livelihood activities affect the fate of children in coastal communities such as existence of fishing and agricultural camps, initiation camps and total freedom to girl child after initiation ceremony;
- Lack of parental care to children in coastal communities.
- Pervasiveness of coastal cultural practices justifies the need for awareness creation.

Initiation is a rite of passage to all girls

Identification of culture in coastal communities was among the objectives of the study. It was revealed that initiation ceremony to girl child is mandatory. Initiation is a rite of passage to a girl child in coastal communities, thus every girl child in the area has to pass through the initiation process. Consequently, after the ceremony the girl child assumed to be matured enough hence attain all the responsibilities of the wife. As it was argued by one of the students within Wama Nakayama Girls Secondary School who participated in the focus group discussion, she was of the views that:

In this area girls are taken to the initiation ceremony at the age of 11 – 13 years. Once one attained the ceremony started to assume all the responsibilities of the wife. Eventually, started to engage in love affairs at a small age and start losing concentration in studies. This cut across to students of all levels meaning primary and secondary schools. While parents in the area assumed that, after the ceremony a girl child is matured enough to start engaging herself in love affairs with either boys of her age or elder ones available in the community' (Focus Group Discussion, Students, Salale Ward, Jan 2022).

It was further explained by the head teacher in the in-depth interview that:

Initiation ceremony affect students as they are taken to the preparation of the ceremony for one month or more in turn students fail to attend classes, the situation affect academic performance (In-depth interview, head teacher, Salale Ward, Jan 2022).

On the contrary, it was further noted by the headmistress during the in- depth interview that:

Very few girls managed to proceed well with classless after initiation ceremony hence managed to complete their studies and keep on being descent girls within the coastal communities. Additionally, initiation ceremony for them is a ritual therefore is hard for a girl child to reject it. Again, the belief attached to the respective ritual is hard to change among parents (In-depth interview, headmistress, Salale Ward, Jan 2022).

Education is provided more to boys rather girls in coastal communities

Findings of the study revealed that in coastal communities education is provided more to boys rather than girls as they are assumed to be responsible in taking care of old parents. In the course of discussing the initiation ceremony in the coastal communities was further revealed that, pervasiveness of the mentioned cultural practice resulted to the education provision based on gender preference. Meaning, education is provided more to boys rather than girls as they are assumed to be responsible in taking care of old parents. As it was further commented by one of the Village Executive Officer in the in depth interview, was of views that:

Boys are given priority in the attainment of education rather than girls, as they are assumed that they will be responsible in taking care of old parents rather than girls. It was further added that boys are considered to be heads of the family and responsible in taking care of the family in all aspects hence given priority in education attainment rather than girls (In-depth Interview, Village Executive Officer, Salale Ward, Jan 2022).

On the other hand, ward education officer within Salale ward, was of the views that:

Boys in coastal communities are not taking education into consideration instead are thinking of engaging themselves in petty business which eventually resulted into dropout from studies. They engage themselves into fishing and charcoal making. While other boys are engaging themselves in petty trading prevailed in the area (In – depth interview, Ward Education Officer, Salale Ward, Jan 2022).

In similar way, in an in- depth interview with head teacher, was of the views that:

Dropout is very high in coastal communities among boys rather than girls as they tend to start doing petty business from standard five, six and seven. In comparison with girls, boys are taking more risks by engaging themselves in various petty

businesses within the coastal communities which include fishing, charcoal making and other petty business within the area. To girls, drop out is associated with early pregnancy and truancy (In-depth interview, head teacher, Salale Ward, Jan 2022).

Livelihood activities affect the fate of children in coastal communities

Study findings further revealed that several factors were mentioned by locals which contributed to the persistent of cultural practises in the study area. In the focus group discussion with male parents in the study area were of the views that:

Initiation ceremony is a historical practice, what we normally practice we have inherited from the past generation to generation so is hard for us to change. However, there are very little changes in the coastal community recently. We have been taught by our elders that girls are for married purposes and boys are considered to be more responsible in searching food and other necessities in the household, such a belief prevail to date to most of us (Focus group discussion, Male parent, Salale Ward, Jan 2022).

It was further added by the female parent in their focus group discussion that:

Common cultural practises such as initiation ceremony to girls have been always there, once you refuse go through the ceremony is hard for a girl to get married in the area; therefore we train our daughters in similar way. We train them through 'Nyakanga' (responsible person in training girls during initiation process within coastal communities). There are some little changes nowadays because knowledge has been provided to us on the importance of education to our kids especially girls. There is an Ngo called Camfed, responsible in the provision of education to community members on the importance of education to children in the area. The other issue is the fact that, there is no mixture of people in this area; we are closely related to most of us and knowing each other and the neighbourhood as well, therefore there is nothing new that we learn from each other in turn we keep on moving with what we have inherited from our elders (Focus group discussion, Female parent, Salale Ward, Jan 2022).

Further more in the discussion with the head teacher in the in-depth interview it was noted that:

Some of the parents in the area tend live their home to either fish camps or farms. They stay outside their home for a month or more leaving aside children taking care of themselves. Examples of fish camps within the area include 'simbaulanga' and 'bunduki' while an example of farm camp is 'makapwani' the place where River Rufiji get into the ocean, therefore locals tend to cultivate rice for subsistence purposes. While parents are in those camps a girl child becomes responsible in taking care of others in the household. In case of hardship, she seeks assistance to either 'bodaboda' boys (those who rides motor cycle in the area) or any other man in the area. They started having an affair at a tender age as they are looking for the money for themselves and young ones at their home (In -depth interview, head teacher, Salale Ward, Jan 2022).

In similar way, students in the focus group discussion were of the views that:

Other parents in the area tend to advice their children to fail the exams so that they stay at home and assist them in various activities like fishing, charcoal making and farming. For girls, they are advised to fail their exams so that they get married early while parents get dowry out of that. In some scenario if you pass the exam you will beaten by parents and other children in the area are bewitched so that they refuse themselves to go to next level of their studies in case they passed exams. This made some of the students to be scared and fail their exams purposefully so as to make their parents happy (Focus group discussion, Boys students, Salale Ward, Jan 2022).

Lack of parental care to children in coastal communities.

In the discussion with various respondents in the study area, it was further noted that there is lack of parental care in most of the household in the area. The situation is highly associated with movement of parents to either fish camps or farms. It was explained by one of the head teacher in the study area in the in-depth interview, was of the views that:

Some parents in the area tend to move to either fish camps or farms for their own daily activities and income generation for the household. The process of shifting to either fishing or farming camps hence a girl child becomes responsible in taking care of the young ones. Also, parents tend to leave behind little amount of money for daily subsistence, in turn children fail to go school on time, others tend to go to school with hunger hence they cannot concentrate in their studies

and others fail to go to school for the entire period whereby parents were out of the household. This situation calls for immediate intervention that every parent in the study area is supposed to be responsible in taking care of children (In –depth Interview, Head teacher, Salale Ward, Jan 2022).

Furthermore, study findings revealed that there is minimal parental care to children in the coastal communities; the situation is highly associated with the nature of their livelihood activities. It was further argued by one of the headmistress in the study area that:

Parental care is crucial to students since through parental care students can concentrate in their studies and pass. However, the nature of economic activities in coastal communities contributed to bad performance among students in their studies. In addition dropout rate increases among children in both primary and secondary schools due to lack of parental care. Parents are suppose to work very close with teachers so as to make sure that students are attending classes as required. For the girls there is a need of having hostels within the school compound so as to make sure girls are safe hence managed to attend classes as required (In –depth Interview, Head mistress, Salale Ward, Jan 2022)

Pervasiveness of coastal cultural practices justify the need for awareness creation

Another objective of the study was to establish the correlation between cultural practices in coastal communities and the role of education in empowering girl child. In that, further discussion with several respondents within the study area revealed that, cultural practice should not interfere with education provision among girls in coastal communities. As it was explained by ward education officer that:

In coastal community education has been given less priority by parents, especially to a girl child, this call for the intervention of educating parents on the importance of education to their children. This will eventually change their mindset, perception and beliefs towards provision of education to a girl child in coastal communities. Girls are only prepared to be mothers and wives at a very small age through initiation ceremony (In –depth Interview, Ward education officer, Salale Ward, Jan 2022).

It was further argued by students at the secondary school in study area in their focus group that:

Some cultural practise, nature of economic activities, soil fertility and minimal interaction with other community resulted into poverty in the area. Eventually, poverty resulted to failure to obtain basic needs at the household level. Consequently children started to look for the income so as to sustain the family. In that, boys start doing small business while girls start having an affair for gaining income. This needs more education to parents so as to stop any bad cultural practise and enforcement should be made to provide education to children especially girls because education is their right. It was further advised that parents should find other ways of getting income instead of relying in farming and fishing activities within coastal communities (Focus group discussion, Secondary school students, Salale Ward, Jan 2022).

It was further added by village executive officer in the in-depth interview that:

Lack of knowledge on the importance of education among girls in coastal communities is connected with the prevailed cultural practise in the area. More education to parents is needed so as to change their mindset towards the importance of education among girls. Because by changing mindset of parents will eventually change children mindset and the entire society as well (In-depth Interview, Village executive officer, Salale Ward, Jan 2022).

This implies that, the identified cultural practise hinder the provision of education to children in coastal communities. Understanding of cultural practise substantiate the need of educating coastal communities on the importance's of education to children especially girls. Therefore, findings of the study revealed that the importance of education outweigh the existing cultural practises.

5. DISCUSSION

This study intends to ascertain the culture of coastal communities and cultural correlation of coastal communities to the role of education in empowering girl child. As indicated in the findings initiation ceremony is the cultural practice that affects provision of girls education in the study area. Similary, Mtwele (2012) was of the views that girls are married immediately after initiation ceremony. Mtweve (2014) added that, attitude of societal members after initiation ceremony are considered that girls are ready for motherhood and marriage. His findings revealed that due to this attitude girl who has passed through the initiation ceremony are discouraged to go back to school by societal members. It has been further

argued by (Masri, 2017) that traditional ceremonies and early marriage affect access of both primary and secondary education among girls. The finding has potential implication for the fate of a girl child in coastal communities hence should be taken into consideration by decision makers.

Findings of the study further revealed that, education is provided more to boys rather than girls as they are assumed to be responsible in taking care of old parents. In a report of United State Agency (2006) stated that there is a strong gender inequality in the provision of education, in that repetition and dropout proportion are significantly higher to girls while completion rate is low. This indicates that, there is strong inequality in education provision in coast communities which eventually affect performance in education between girls and boys. Furthermore, it has been noted by (Harrison, 2010) that gender inequality in coastal communities is constructed through informal and unwritten norms.

Study findings further revealed that livelihood activities affect the education provision of children in coastal communities such as existence of fishing and agricultural camps, initiation camps and total freedom to girl child after initiation ceremony. It has been noted by Dani & De Haan (2008) in their study that to achieve gender equality in Modurese women living on the coast due to their low socio-economic status. The situation necessitate for the economic empowerment of the coastal families. In that, girls should be empowered so that they avoid drop out from school or entering into early marriage. It has been further reported in ILO 2006, the report gave an example of educational inequality is access in education and gender gap in coastal areas. In that, it has been stated that, the area has low quality of education and the relevance of education is influenced by inability to create a quality learning process.

The study was further revealed that there is lack of parental care to children in the study area. The situation is linked up with the tendency of leaving home for a month or more for either fishing or farming activities. Similarly, other researchers have argued that the dominant factor that causing school dropout in coastal communities including lack of parental care (Sobo, 2012), societal member view factor towards education (Viles & Spencer, 2014) and parental nature of socio-economic activities such as fishing and farmers (Coulthard *et al.*, 2011). Additionally, in coastal communities economic problems become a common problem inherent in coastal communities (Viles & Spencer, 2014). It has been further reported in URT (2005a) that coastal communities highly rely on artisanal fishing, sea weed farming, livestock husbandry, petty trading and small holder faming for subsistence.

Pervasiveness of coastal cultural practices justify the need for awareness creation on the importance's' of education especially to girls in coastal communities. It has been further argued by Santha (2008) that fishermen and their children still have a low education hence is difficult for them to find alternative work. While Moshy & Bryceson (2016) was of the views that the poverty experienced by the coastal communities can be seen from the livelihood of its inhabitants. Furthermore, it has been argued that, due to strong influence of their culture many children tend to drop out of school to pursue a life that they feel will provide a better living for them. To them education is an option (Mangora & Shalli ,2006). In URT (2005a), has been reported that livelihoods of the coastal communities in Tanzania are characterized by low living standard with low per capita of less than USD 100, large families and high illiteracy level. On the contrary, in the Human Development Report (2011) it has been reported that, education is one of the initiatives in order to improve the quality of human life. Thus, education intends to humanize human beings, mature human beings, behavioral change and improve human quality for better. Eventually, education will support peoples' lives in the future.

6. CONCLUSION

This study was carried out so as to ascertain the culture of coastal communities and cultural correlation of coastal communities to the role of education in empowering girl child. The study revealed that, initiation ceremony is a common cultural practise in the area which consequently affects education attainment to a girl child. The study further revealed that the pervasiveness of the cultural practise, existence of fishing and farming camps have consequently affect the education provision to a girl child. It was further revealed that, lack of parental care and total freedom of a girl child after initiation ceremony resulted to school dropout and early pregnancies to girls. For boys the situation made them to lack concentration in their studies hence affects their academic performance. The findings of the study further revealed that, poverty to household found in the study area made children to either attend classes with hunger while others fail to attend classes; this resulted to rise in drop out level in the study area. It was revealed that education provision to children at the household in the area is based on gender, meaning boys are given more priority rather than girls. Study findings further revealed that, pervasiveness of coastal cultural practices justify the need for awareness creation on the importance's' of education especially to girls in coastal communities.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

From the findings, this study recommends the following, some cultural practises in coastal communities should be stopped such as initiation ceremony to girls, education should be provided to parents on the impotencies of education to girls and parents should be responsible in taking care of children especially girls. This will in turn change their parents' perception, beliefs and attitude towards education provision; consequently drop out level will decrease in coastal communities. The study, further recommends that, at the family level, a girl child should be given education opportunity in similar way as boy child given. The study recommends further that, locals should be educated on the importance of involving themselves into various economic activities instead of relying on fishing and cultivation of rice for substance. It was further recommended by this study that, the government, through policies should be implemented so as to enforce the provision of education to a girl child, in coastal communities. In that, education provision should taken as a right to a girl child, hence every girl child in the area should get education in similar way as boy child get. Lastly, the study recommends that, the government and other education stakeholders should sensitize community on the need and significance of a girl child education in coastal communities. This is because education brings reduction in inequalities and functions as a means of improving their status within the society.

Ethical approval: All procedures performed in studies involving human participants were by the ethical standards of the institutional and national research committee and with the 1964 Helsinki declaration and its later amendments or comparable ethical standards. This article does not contain any studies with animals performed by any of the authors.

Informed consent: Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

Acknowledgements: The authors wish to appreciate all respondents for sharing their experiences that help us increase our understanding in culture of coastal communities and cultural correlation of coastal communities to the role of education in empowering girl child. We also thanks education officers in all visited sites that include Kibiti District Council, Salale ward officers include ward executive officer, ward education officer, village executive officers, village chair persons, head teachers, headmistress, parents and students from both primary and secondary schools. We also thank the management of the Mwalimu Nyerere Memorial Academy for the support we received during the execution of this study.

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